

DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING THE ACTIVITY OF AGRICULTURAL ENTERPRISES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13969863>

Abstract. The article analyzes the innovative ways of improving labor relations during the activity of agricultural enterprises

Key words: economic efficiency, profitability, key indicators, profit, material cost, income.

INTRODUCTION. In recent years, the disparity between the prices of the products grown in agriculture and the prices of the industrial products produced in industry and used in agriculture is the reason for the need to further improve the state support measures for the industry in accordance with the market requirements and other such issues are the basis for the price of agricultural products to exceed the level of demand.

The development of the country's economy and the improvement of the material well-being of workers are directly related to the reforms implemented not only in the economic sphere, but in many ways in the social sphere. In this matter, increasing the volume and quality of the products produced in the network, and most importantly, gradually optimizing the cost of the product, has a special place.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. A number of leading agrarian economists and theoreticians of our republic, including: A.A.Abdug'aniev, A.A.Shokirov, A.Joraev, A.Z.Zokirov, A.S.Samutali, D.Q.Ahmedov, N.S. Khushmatov, R.V. Abdullaev, R.Kh. Khusanov, F.Q.Qayumov, F.Kh.Nazarova, CH.M.Murodov, E.J.Yusupov, O'.P.Umurzakov, Q.A.Khasanjanov, Q.A.Choriev and others conducted scientific research.

RESULTS. Based on the opinions and opinions of scientists who have conducted research on the methodology of economic efficiency evaluation until now, they can be conditionally divided into two groups. Scientists belonging to the first group believe that the criterion indicator of economic efficiency should be the only one.

There is an inextricable connection between the growth of the expenses spent in agriculture and the growth of the prices of the grown products. Therefore, it is necessary to try to spend every soum rationally, in accordance with the purpose, that is, to save material, money, and labor costs, thereby achieving a reduction in the cost of produced products, performed work and services.

We also believe that in order to optimize the price of agricultural products, we should pay attention to the following:

- to ensure timely and high-quality execution of all agro-technological activities by using all the means of production available in the farming and animal husbandry industries wisely and effectively throughout the year;
- further development of seed production based on the creation of quick-ripening, efficient varieties of crops that require little water, ensuring breeding of productive breeds of

livestock; reducing the disparity between the prices of industrial enterprises used in agriculture and agricultural products

- gradual reduction of the disparity between the prices of resources produced by industrial enterprises used in agriculture and the prices set for agricultural products;
- increasing the level of mechanization and automation of production processes as a result of the introduction of new techniques and effective technologies that save production costs, reducing live labor costs;
- to ensure quality and effective solutions to issues related to irrigation, land reclamation and chemization;
- improvement of effective forms of labor organization and incentive system;
- to achieve an increase in the productivity of crops and productivity of livestock;
- improvement of the most effective forms of labor organization and incentive system in farms;
- ensuring the competitiveness of agricultural products, etc.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, it can be noted that sufficient supply of the necessary labor resources of the enterprises, their rational use and a high level of labor productivity are of great importance for increasing the volume of products and increasing production efficiency. In particular, the volume and timely completion of all work, the efficiency of the use of equipment, machines, mechanisms and, as a result, the volume of product production, its cost and a number of other economic indicators, ensure that enterprises are provided with labor resources and from them depends on effective use.

In the conditions of the market economy, when assessing the efficiency of the use of labor resources in the enterprise, the indicator of personnel profitability (the ratio of profit to the average annual number of industrial and production personnel) is of great importance. therefore, we developed a factor model of this indicator.

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